

Academic Production Analysis On Content Curation

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Abstract-This essay attempts to examine the science output on content curation, studying its temporal progression, facets of authorship such as cooperation with authors and their affiliations, reviews most important journals and congresses as well as more thematically handled. Among the findings, we illustrated the multidisciplinary of content curation, where we find examples from journalism to engineering and informatics, also from education to documentation, distribution authorship and affiliations in several research centres, as well as clear thematic connexion ethics with social networking that are most used for dissemination.

Keywords-Content curation, Academic Production, Bibliometric, Authorship, Scientific magazines, Research topics, Keyword analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Content curation (or content curation) is a recently emerging specialty related to the selection and processing of digital information, the origin of which is usually set in 2009 in Manifesto for the content curator (Bhargava, 2009), although there are some previous vestiges or precedents of the use of the term "curation". In it, its author, professional and marketing teacher, points out the need for a new professional practice that specializes in selecting content that is most relevant to a given audience, given the informational environment of web content saturation. This initial concept has been extended in the second decade of the 21st century since that origin in the digital marketing sector to other areas and professional and academic fields, such as journalism and communication (Guerrini, 2013), engineering and

computer science (De Roure et al, 2010), information and documentation (Parra-Valero, 2017), or education (Jute) árez Popoca, Torres Gastelú and Herrera Díaz, 2017); among others. Under the common denominator of being a technique or a specialty focused on filtering or selecting digital content, from the various approaches and disciplines that have become interested in it, different accents have also been placed: from social healing or healing that takes place in social media (Bruns, 2018), to news curation or that carried out by digital journalistic media (Cui and Liu, 2017), to curating content as a librarian's competition (Martínez-Cañadas, 2017), or their paper in learning (Caeiro et al., 2013), or in program or software design specialized in curing (Yasumoto, Yamaguchi and Shigeno, 2016), etc. In addition, he has been credited on several occasions with an essential or central role, and not at all peripheral or marginal, in the development and updating of various disciplines, as is the case with journalism: "in the 21st century ... good journalism cannot be done without journalistic healing" (Guallar and Codina, 2018). Thus, in a context such as the current one of expansion, diversification and value of the concept of content curation, 10 years after its first appearance, we found it appropriate to analyse its presence in academic research to determine the extent of scientific interest in an innovative professional activity. For this purpose, we have chosen to present in this paper an analysis approach of academic production on this field, bibliometric orientation. The conduct of bibliometric studies to explore the scientific landscape in a given discipline or thematic specialty is increasingly common, and hundreds of examples of such diverse topics can be found such as gender studies (Dehdarirad et al, 2015), open educational practices (Koseoglu and Bozkurt, 2018), social media (Kapoor, 2011) 7; Gálvez, 2019), the most common issues in documentation (Liu and Yang, 2019), or digital media interactivity (Abadal and Guallar, 2018). The usefulness of these studies is clear, as they show which are the main authors of the field, the most used journals, the collaborations between authors, the thematic orientations, etc. This type of approach does not go into depth in the content analysis that would be carried out in a bibliographic review, but instead they are capable of showing some of the most important guidelines of bibliographic production in a specific discipline or subject, as we will show below This article wants to follow this line and aims to analyse the scientific production on content curation to know several fundamental dimensions of it, such as its temporal evolution, authorship aspects (including collaborations between authors and their affiliations), identification of the most prominent publications (be they magazines or conferences) and of the most important topics discussed. In this way, this kind of analysis can reflect the dimensions of a discipline, in this case of content curation, not only to help understand it, but so that other researchers in the same field can better guide their work, thus as the decision making of actors involved in it.

II. METHODOLOGY

The bibliometric analysis has taken as a reference the multidisciplinary database Scopus (Elsevier, <https://www.scopus.com/sources>), which indexes 38,000 academic journals and thus has a broader representation and with a better specialization in social sciences and than that included in Web of Science, which indexes a total of 21,200 journals in its Core

Collection (<https://mjl.clarivate.com/search-results>). Google Scholar has not been used either because, despite the inclusion in it of an even greater number of sources (since, in addition to journals, it also contains books), it does not have any standardization system for bibliographic records (names of the authors, affiliations, etc.) nor does it collect the thematic tags (keywords) of the documents, which are essential to be able to carry out our bibliometric analysis. The terms used in the consultation were "content curation" and "content curator", also using the two variants of the activity more specifically related to the field of journalism, since in this context the term "curation" is usually also combined with the terms "news" or "journalism". The study of "data curation" has been discarded since it is considered that this concept fundamentally addresses a specific approach different from the one studied here, more linked to digital preservation in areas such as the management of research data. See this distinction, for example in: Guallar and Leiva-Aguilera, 2013, p. 22, or a bibliometric investigation on the subject of data curation in Corral, Kennan and Afzal, 2013. At first, the query was limited to the keyword field (KEY) but due to the low number of results (82 documents) it was decided to expand it to the title, summary and keywords fields. Thus, the resulting search equation (which can be reproduced by anyone on the Scopus advanced search page) is as follows: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("content curation" OR "news curation" OR "journalistic curation" OR "content curator") The total of records found was 145. After reviewing the records, a duplicate document was found, and another that did not fit the theme, which were eliminated, so the final result is 143. The same query in Web of Science collected 118 documents (a significantly lower proportion) and in Google Scholar (limiting the search terms to the title field) there were 338 documents (with the aforementioned difficulties when downloading the records and the absence of standardization of the bibliographic information they contain). No time limitation has been applied. Therefore, in the final selection of publications that are the object of analysis, items from any year can be found, although, as we will see, significant production begins in 2013. The indicators to be analysed are the following: temporal evolution, authorship, affiliation, type of document, language, magazine, most cited articles and topics. In this way, a mapping of the most important dimensions of the existing publications on the subject analysed is obtained. Due to the total number of records found, the global sum of occurrences is analysed and commented on for each of the indicators. The approach made to the results is quantitative. Spreadsheets with bibliographic references have been used to exploit the results, which have allowed the generation of tables for each of the aforementioned indicators. On the other hand, the VOSviewer program (van Eck, 2010) developed at the University of Leiden has also been used, which serves to generate networks with bibliographic data (co-authorship maps, indexing terms, etc.) that are shown in very visual and understandable representations.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Next, the results will be discussed for each of the aforementioned indicators. Tables come directly from the data downloaded from Scopus and display maps they have been generated by VOSviewer. Next to the tables the total units are indicated analysed (either the publications, the authors, etc.).

Temporal evolution

The first document located dates from 2010 and in the first two years the annual number of publications is very low (1-2), until in 2012 we already found 7 documents, and in the following years (2013-2018) the number is significantly higher (between 14 and 38 documents per year), being the maximum of 38 in 2016. This indicates that in the last 6 years, a window that is used frequently in studies of this guy, we have the largest backlog of posts, with a total of 133 references. This identified annual distribution confirms the advanced observation in other studies, on the origin and evolution of the specialty (Guallar; Leiva-Aguilera, 2013): after the “official” appearance of the content curation concept in publications professionals at the end of 2009 with “Manifesto for the content curator” (Bhargava, 2009), I don't know appreciates a meaningful use of the concept in the academic field until 2012 (7 occurrences), and especially, 2013 (14 occurrences), year from of which the specialty in the research with an average in the period 2013- 2018, of 22 publications per year in magazines collected in Scopus.

<i>Year</i>	<i>Hits</i>
2010	1
2011	2
2012	7
2013	14
2014	17
2015	15
2016	38
2017	20
2018	29

Table 1 Annual production (n = 143)

Authorship

The number of researchers who have published on the subject studied in publications academic indexed in Scopus is 438. Of them, a very important number, 397, have published just one item. There are 34 researchers who have published two articles, and 7 more have published three or more jobs: this is Zhang and Wu (five articles), Bruns, Chen, Jian and Zhang (three). The authors' relationship with two articles or more and their affiliation is shown in Table 2. There are therefore not a few very prominent figures in production on the rest of authors on this subject, but rather it is observed the existence of a group of 43 researchers who have been interested in the subject, of which 6 of them stand out. In the set

of authors shown in the table, it is worth noting the absence of some very acquaintances on the subject of content curation. The reason is that they have published mainly in the professional field in non-academic publications or in dissemination monographs, and that, therefore, they do not appear here. It would be the case of authors like Rosenbaum or Bhaskar for example, with very popular monographs (Rosenbaum, 2011; Bhaskar, 2016). Exceptions to this dynamic would be the cases of authors like Bruns and Guallar, who have combined the academic approach with that of disclosure or essay (Bruns; 2018; Guallar and Leiva-Aguilera, 2013). By work centers of the authors, highlights the Beijing University of Technology (China), which appears linked to the highest number of authorship of this table (7), although it must be specified that in several cases are multiple authorship of 5 and 6 researchers per article. Along with it, appreciates the presence of an important variety from centers in the United States, from various countries Europeans, as well as Queensland University of Technology of Australia, workplace of Bruns. The analysis of the co-authorship (figure 1, generated via VOSviewer) allows you to view which are the relationships between researchers. No However, what stands out most is that there is little or no interrelation between the different clusters. The figure shows 18 clusters, especially highlighting that of Chinese authors as the most numerous in terms of authors and with various interrelations internal. Now how do I know can verify the existence of relationships between the various groups. On the other hand, if we consider the affiliation of the all authors who have published on the thematic (and not only that of the authors with the most publications, as in table 2), you can see in table 3 the centers that group more authors on the field (with 5 or more authors). Two entities from the United Kingdom stand out (University of Cambridge and University of London) followed distance learning by Beijing University of Technology from China, and 2 more centers from the Kingdom United (University of Manchester and Rothamsted Research) and 2 from the United States (universities Northwestern and Texas). There is a clear predominance of the universities and only three appear research centers. As in previous cases, an important geographic diversity is observed, in Europe, America and Asia, although in this case is the centers of a country, the United Kingdom, who tend to concentrate more authorship.

Author	Affiliation	Hits
Wu, L Beijing University of Technology,	Beijing, China	6
Zhang, D Beijing University of Technology,	Beijing University of Technology, China / California State University, Sacramento, Estados Unidos	5

Table 2 Authors with the most publications on the subject (n => 2)

Countries

If we analyse the distribution of authorship all the articles by country, it is verified than the United States with 105 mentions and the Kingdom United with 91 they clearly stand out from

the rest. Next, Spain appears (43 mentions) that is halfway to a group of four countries (Japan, China, Germany and South Korea) that are in the range of between 19 and 25 mentions. We also note that the publication on content curation is widely distributed worldwide, with the presence of authors from countries of the four continents (all but Africa) among the top positions.

<i>Center</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Automatic.</i>
University of Cambridge	The United Kingdom	28
University of London	The United Kingdom	21
Peking University of Technology	China	12
University of Manchester	The United Kingdom	11
Northwestern University	The United States	9
Rothamsted Research	The United Kingdom	8
University of Texas	The United States	8
Dublin University College	Ireland	8
Keio University	Japan	7
University Carlos III of Madrid	Spain	7
Universidade of Vigo	Spain	7
Université du Luxemburg	Luxembourg	6
University of Maryland	The United States	6
Università I gave Florence	Italy	5
University of Electro- Communications, Tokyo	Japan	5
Language Technology Lab, Berlin	Germany	5
Nara Institute of Science and Technology	Japan	5

Table 3 Affiliations by authors (n => 5)

Document type

Journal articles constitute the type of document most used to post about this topic, with about half of the posts (47%), being also very remarkable the percentage of papers submitted to congresses (40%). The latter can be explained by the presence of publications with a focus information systems and technology, fields in which congresses are a widely used channel for the dissemination of results. For other part, the proportion of papers presented as a book chapter it is clearly low.

Country	Mentions
The United States	105
The United Kingdom	91
Spain	43
Japan	25
China	20
Germany	19
South Korea	19
France	14
Australia	11
Ireland	11
Italy	11
Portugal	11
Luxembourg	8
Canada	7
Holland	7
Switzerland	7
Austria	6
Brazil	6
India	5
Poland	5

Table 4 Distribution of authors by country (n => 5)

Language

Regarding the language used in the documents, English stands out in the majority (with 131 91%), and only Spanish, although far away (9 jobs, 6%), has a somewhat remarkable presence, with a sphere of influence focused on Spain and Latin America.

<i>Document type</i>	<i>Hits</i>	<i>%</i>
Article of magazine	68	47,55
Paper in congress	58	40,55
Book chapter	6	4,19
Others	11	7,69

Table 5 Production by type of document (n = 143)

It is surprising, on the other hand, that they only appear four more languages, and in some proportions insignificant. It should be noted that in a case of a magazine that publishes in English and Spanish, has assigned an article to the English version, the considered in that case as official.

<i>Language</i>	<i>Hits</i>	<i>%</i>
English	131	91,60
Spanish	9	6,29
Alemán	1	0,69
Catalan	1	0,69
French	1	0,69
Japanese	1	0,69

Table 6 Production by language (n = 143)

Magazines and Conferences

The total number of journals and conferences that have published some work is 109, with a notable dispersion, since 92 of them (84.4%) only have published a text on the subject.

<i>Magazines</i>	<i>Hits</i>	<i>Country</i>
The professional of the information	5	Spain
Studies on the journalistic message	3	Spain
Annals of Emergency Medicine	2	The USA
Business Information Review	2	The USA
Journalism digitalis	2	UK
EContent	2	The USA
Information Communication and Society	2	UK

Average New and Society	2	The USA
Nucleic Acids Research	2	UK
Performance Evaluation Review	2	The USA
<i>Congresses</i>	8	
Lecture Notes in Computer Science*		
CEUR Workshop Proceedings	7	
ACM International Conference Proceeding Series	3	
Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing	3	
Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings	3	
TVX 2016 - Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Interactive for Experiences TV and Online Video	2	

Table 7 Scientific journals and conference proceedings with more jobs (from 2)

Table 7 shows the 16 that have been published 2 or more works on the subject. They are two different typologies: scientific journals and proceedings congresses. In the first case it is a group of 10 journals, published in three countries: half of which are from the United States, 3 from the United Kingdom and 2 from Spain, which are nonetheless those that occupy the first two places of the ranking: The Information and Studies professional about the journalistic message. Although Communication magazines predominate (5), the set accounts for the enormous variety of approaches of content curation, with magazines too Business, Documentation, IT, Information systems, Medicine or Biochemistry. As for congresses, in this case it is of events in all cases in the fields of Engineering and Informatics, sectors in which, as is known, the minutes of scientific meetings They are the main channel of academic communication, highlighting two of them: Lecture Notes in Computer Science and CEUR Workshop Proceedings.

<i>Autores</i>	<i>Título</i>	<i>Año</i>	<i>Título de la fuente</i>	<i>Citas</i>
unter S. et al	InterPro in 2011: New developments in the family and domain prediction database	2012	Nucleic Acids Research	753
Rotman D., et al	Supporting content curation communities: The case of the Encyclopedia of Life	2012	Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology	30
Zhong C., Shah S., Sundaravadivelan K., Sastry N.	Sharing the loves: Understanding the how and why of online content curation	2013	Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media, ICWSM 2013	29
De Roure D., et al.	Towards open science: The myExperiment approach	2010	Concurrency Computation Practice and Experience	23
Yasumoto K., Yamaguchi H., Shigeno H.	Survey of real-time processing technologies of IoT data streams	2016	Journal of Information Processing	20
Roland D., Spurr J., Cabrera D.	Preliminary evidence for the emergence of a health care online community of practice...	2017	Journal of Medical Internet Research	12
Hawkins C.M., DeLaO A.J., Hung C.	Social Media and the Patient Experience	2016	Journal of the American College of Radiology	12
Sørensen I.E.	Channels as content curators: Multiplatform strategies for documentary film and factual content in British public service broadcasting	2014	European Journal of Communication	12
Mansell R.	Employing digital crowdsourced information resources: Managing the emerging information commons	2013	International Journal of the Commons	12

Bruns A., Highfield T.	From news blogs to news on Twitter: Gatewatching and collaborative news curation	2015	Handbook of Digital Politics	11
Wolff A., Mulholland P.	Curation, curation, curation	2013	Proceedings of the 3rd Narrative and Hypertext Workshop Held at the ACM Conference on Hypertext and Social Media, NHT 2013	11
Morbidoni C., et al	Introducing the semlib project: Semantic web tools for digital libraries	2011	CEUR Workshop Proceedings	11
De Vito M.A., Gergle D., Birnholtz J.	"Algorithms ruin everything": #RIPTwitter, folk theories, and resistance to algorithmic change in social media	2017	Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings	10
Szymanski M., et al	5SRNAdb: An information resource for 5S ribosomal RNAs	2016	Nucleic Acids Research	10
Gawron P., et al.	MINERVA—A platform for visualization and curation of molecular interaction networks	2016	npj Systems Biology and Applications	9
Diakopoulos N.	The editor's eye: Curation and comment relevance on the New York Times	2015	CSCW 2015 - Proceedings of the 2015 ACM International Conference on Computer- Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing	9
Caeiro-Rodríguez M., et al	AREA: A social curation platform for open educational resources and lesson plans	2013	Proceedings - Frontiers in Education Conference, FIE	9

Table 8 Most cited works (first 18) (n => 9)

Most cited articles

Although there are a variety of approaches to content curation, among the most popular articles cited predominate those of those disciplines that have a greater impact and greater activity scientific, as is the case of the first work of the ranking (of chemistry) that stands out in quotes about the rest, as well as various medical jobs and computer science. Among the latter, one can appreciate different system developments presented at conferences on technology and informatics. On the other hand, with a communication approach we find the works of Bruns, Zhong, Rotman or Sorensen. From the point of view of the scope of Social Communication and Sciences of the Documentation, although they are represented they are not a dominant group. This is can see as a clear development opportunity of research in this dimension, maximum if we take into account, as we will see from the next section, the weight of the keywords related.

Thematic

Table 9 and Figure 2 show the 36 terms appearing at least five times in the field keywords (either Author keywords or Indexed keywords). The central keyword is content curation (88 occurrences), as expected, according to the consultation made in the Scopus database. Denotes what the concept is central to the subject studied and that it is always present predominantly in the investigation. The map of the themes (figure 2) clearly indicates that content curation is the central node of the largest thematic cluster of terms. Some variations of the previous term also appear on the list, as are curation, digital curation and news curation. Then it also appears in a relevant way the term Social media (41), which shows clearly the importance of healing content in relation to social media. This term is also the node of the second cluster of thematic relationships between documents, as shown in figure 2. They are also notable terms, with more than 10 occurrences: Internet, Social networking, Recommender systems, Crowdsourcing, Digital libraries and Social networks. It is therefore about some very broad concepts (Internet) along with others that represent very specific areas of action (Digital libraries) or very specific specialties (Crowdsourcing, Recommender systems).

<i>Keyword</i>	<i>Total Hits</i>
Content Curation	88
Social Media	41
Curation	35
Internet	26
Social Networking (online)	25
Human/s*	17
Recommender Systems	11
Crowdsourcing	10
Digital Libraries	10

Social Networks	10
Education	9
Digital Content	7
Digital Curation	7
E-learning	7
Journalism	7
Learning	7
Article	6
Artificial Intelligence	6
Blogs	6
Collaboration	6
Design	6
Learning Systems	6
Online Systems	6
Priority Journal	6
Students	6
United States	6
Emergency Medicine	5
Marketing	5
Mass Media	5
Medical Education	5
News Curation	5
Semantic Web	5
Storytelling	5
Teaching	5
User Interfaces	5
Web 2.0	5

Table 9 Most frequent terms

With less occurrences appear other terms that refer to disciplines or specialties (Education, Elearning, Journalism, Medicine, Artificial Intelligence...). Overall, the diversity of themes and fields of action in which is applied or in which the healing of contents, from Journalism

to Medicine, from Education to Libraries, and with a strong protagonism, of all of them, of everything that related to Social media.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

From the results obtained, some conclusions can be highlighted. Regarding the temporal evolution, there has been a notable growth in publications on this subject as of 2013, which has continued to grow almost until the moment of the analysis, which shows the growing importance of this field, despite to be such a specific specialty. Regarding authorship, there are not a few authors that stand out from the rest, but authorship is widely distributed, highlighting in any case a group of researchers affiliated with Chinese universities, specifically with the University of Beijing, although also there are several prominent Anglo-Saxon universities such as the British in Cambridge and London and the North American in Queensland and New York. By countries, those with the largest number of authors interested in the subject are the United States and the United Kingdom, with Spain already appearing in third place. The language used predominantly in the publications analysed is English, from Education to Libraries, and with a strong role, among all of them, in everything related to Social Media. almost 91% and then Spanish, with 6%. The other localized languages do not reach 1%. In the list of magazines that have published more texts on this topic, two Spanish magazines stand out, *El Profesional de la Información* and *Estudios sobre el Correo Periodístico*. Next, with the same number of publications (2, the chosen base) appears a group of Anglo-Saxon publications. Regarding the themes, the curation of content shows a great transversality at present since it has been treated from different approaches and disciplines, from journalism to engineering and computer science, or from education to libraries, appearing in any case its relationship with Social media very prominent. In this way, the characterization that we have been able to show of the content curation in terms of the academic publications that it has generated, allows us to better understand this field of studies and professional, at the same time that it helps researchers and actors in this field to take decisions that can go from the follow-up of magazines, to points where to deepen the field with greater possibilities of success. Finally, we want to point out that analysis of this kind, in addition to significant intrinsic contributions such as those mentioned, can provide guidance on research gaps and, therefore, new opportunities. The analysis of some of the dimensions of our results clearly show the research opportunities both in the documentation sciences and in social communication. The reason is that we have seen that, despite content curation being a topic closely linked to both disciplines, its presence on the other hand is relatively small in magazines in the aforementioned fields. This leads us to believe, as a conjecture, that we need more research at the intersection between content curation and social communication on the one hand, and content curation and documentation sciences on the other. This does not exclude, but rather encourages, multidisciplinary research that covers the intersection between the three areas. In this case, we hope that our work can be a useful starting point for other researchers who wish to delve into it.

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